

On a generalized sum of the Mersenne Numbers

Amelia Carolina Sparavigna

Politecnico di Torino

Abstract Here we discuss the Mersenne numbers to give an example of a generalized sum. Using this sum, a recurrence relation is given.

Keywords Generalized sums, Mersenne numbers.

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.1250048

Written in Turin, on May 20, 2018

Of generalized sums of numbers, we have given some examples in previous works [1-3]. Here we propose the study of the Mersenne Numbers, using the same approach. About these numbers, a large literature exists (see for instance that given in [4]). The form of the numbers is that of a power of two minus 1. Among them we find the Mersenne primes. The numbers are named after Marin Mersenne (1588 – 1648), a French Minim friar, who studied them in the early 17th century.

Mersenne numbers are:

$$M_n = 2^n - 1$$

Let us consider them to give an example of generalized sum. We can start from the following calculus:

$$\begin{aligned} M_{m+n} &= 2^{m+n} - 1 \\ M_{m+n} &= 2^{m+n} - 1 = 2^m 2^n - 1 = 2^m 2^n - 1 - 2^m + 2^m - 2^n + 2^n - 1 + 1 = 2^m (2^n - 1) - 1 + 2^m - 2^n + 1 + 2^n - 1 \\ M_{m+n} &= (2^m - 1)(2^n - 1) + 2^m - 1 + 2^n - 1 \end{aligned}$$

Therefore, we can write the following generalized sum:

$$M_{m+n} = M_m \oplus M_n = (2^m - 1)(2^n - 1) + (2^m - 1) + (2^n - 1)$$

or:

$$(1) \quad M_{m+n} = M_m \oplus M_n = M_m + M_n + M_m M_n$$

This is a generalized sum that we find in the case of the multiplicative groups (for the use of multiplicative groups in statistics and statistical mechanics see [5,6]).

Using (1), for the Mersenne numbers we can imagine the following recursive relation:

$$M_{n+1} = M_n \oplus M_1 = M_n + M_1 + M_n M_1$$

That is:

$$2^{n+1} - 1 = (2^n - 1) + (2^1 - 1) + (2^n - 1)(2^1 - 1) = 2^n + 2^{n+1} - 2^n - 2 + 1 = 2^{n+1} - 1$$

The sum (1) is associative, so that:

$$M_m \oplus M_n \oplus M_l = M_m + M_n + M_l + M_m M_n + M_n M_l + M_m M_l + M_m M_n M_l$$

We cannot have a group of the Mersenne numbers, without considering also the opposites of them, so that:

$$0 = M_n \oplus \text{Opposite}(M_n)$$

Therefore:

$$\text{Opposite}(M_n) = -\frac{M_n}{M_n + 1} = M_{-n}$$

Explicitly:

$$\text{Opposite}(2^n - 1) = -\frac{(2^n - 1)}{(2^n - 1) + 1} = \frac{(-2^n + 1)}{2^n} = 2^{-n} - 1$$

These numbers are the Mersenne numbers with a negative exponent. So we have:

$$M_{nnn} = M_n \oplus M_{-n} = M_n + M_{-n} + M_n M_{-n}$$

$$0 = 2^0 - 1 = (2^n - 1) + (2^{-n} - 1) + (2^n - 1)(2^{-n} - 1) = 2^n + 2^{-n} - 2 + 2^n 2^{-n} - 2^{-n} - 2^n + 1 = 0$$

References

1. Sparavigna, A. C. (2018). Generalized Sums Based on Transcendental Functions. Zenodo . DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.1250020
2. Sparavigna, A. C. (2018). On the generalized sum of the symmetric q-integers. Zenodo. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.1248959

Zenodo 10.5281/zenodo.1250048

3. Sparavigna, A. C. (2018). ON THE ADDITIVE GROUP OF q-INTEGERS. Zenodo . DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.1245849
4. Weisstein, Eric W. "Mersenne Number." From MathWorld--A Wolfram Web Resource. <http://mathworld.wolfram.com/MersenneNumber.html>
5. Sicuro, G., & Tempesta, P. (2016). Groups, information theory, and Einstein's likelihood principle. Phys. Rev. E 93, 040101(R).
6. Curado, E. M., Tempesta, P., & Tsallis, C. (2016). A new entropy based on a group-theoretical structure. Annals of Physics, 366, 22-31.